

Nanostructured gelatin-gellan inks double reinforced with cellulose nanofibrils and graphene derivatives for 3D printing in bone regeneration applications

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ABSTRACT

Although 3D printing has become a prominent technique for fabricating scaffolds for bone tissue engineering (BTE), the development of inks capable of producing constructs with high biocompatibility, mineralization capabilities, and adequate mechanical properties remains a significant challenge. This study investigates the fabrication of scaffolds using 3D printing inks based on gelatin and gellan gum, reinforced with cellulose nanofibrils (GC), and two different functionalized graphene-based materials, i.e., carboxylated graphene oxide (GC-CBX), aminated reduced graphene oxide (GC-AMN), or both derivatives (GC-CBX/AMN). Through a dual cross-linking strategy, the 3D constructs demonstrated overall improved performance, with GC-CBX/AMN scaffolds exhibiting the best printing fidelity, optimal porosity, proper degradation rate and swelling kinetics, and the highest tensile strength. Finally, these samples exhibited excellent biocompatibility and the highest mineralization capacity. These results offer novel insights into the development of functional formulations for bone regeneration and provide a new strategy for advancing scaffold ink fabrication for BTE.

1. Introduction

Bone is a structurally complex tissue that plays a fundamental role in locomotor function, protection of vital organs, and maintenance of calcium homeostasis [1,2]. Although bone exhibits remodeling and regenerative abilities for small defects through a series of organized physiological events, when facing major health issues caused by accidents or congenital diseases, its self-regenerative capacities are

insufficient. Therefore, critical-size bone defects are treated using a range of clinical methods, one of the most frequently used being the employment of bone substitutes. Such substitutes provide structural support and stimulate migration and recruitment of osteoprogenitor cells for the formation of extracellular matrix (ECM) [3–5]. The gold standard is represented by the use of autografts; however, limitations related to restricted availability have resulted in an ongoing search for alternative treatments through bone tissue engineering (BTE) [2,6].

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BTE uses scaffolds specifically designed to temporarily replace the ECM of the affected tissue. Thus, the scaffold should simulate the composition of natural bone, comprising an inorganic component that provides strength and stiffness, giving bone the ability to resist deformations, and an organic component that provides toughness through energy absorption [7–9]. One of the most widely used materials in BTE is gelatin, a tripeptide polymer obtained by the partial hydrolysis of collagen, which is abundant in arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (Arg-Gly-Asp) sequences that provide adhesion sites and a microenvironment suitable for cell survival and adhesion [4,10]. In comparison with collagen, gelatin presents improved processability and solubility properties, and by the partial denaturation process, the immunogenic risk of the biomaterial is significantly reduced [11–13]. Moreover, gelatin can be modified more effectively with methacrylic groups to obtain a photopolymerizable material. However, the methacrylation process can induce cytotoxicity and substantially increase the production cost of the grafting structures [14,15]. Nevertheless, while gelatin provides increased bioactivity to the formulations, it poses limitations on other aspects, like filament formation properties and structural stability. Therefore, the use of multicomponent formulations has become the standard for achieving proper rheological and structural characteristics. Several studies reported that the addition of polysaccharides exhibits the proper properties that contribute to the consistency and stability of the structures, making them excellent candidates for 3D printing bone replacement substituents [16,17]. Among the most commonly used polysaccharides in bone tissue regeneration structures are chitosan, alginates, pectin, and gellan gum. Alginates are often employed due to their ability to improve the printability of an ink formulation, although studies have indicated limitations regarding the long-term mechanical strength of these substituents [18–20]. Likewise, pectin has been used due to its availability and beneficial properties in modulating cellular responses, yet it does not generate the improved rheological properties, limiting shape fidelity and structure stability [21,22]. Another polysaccharide, chitosan, also presents limitations regarding solubility conditions and gelation capabilities [23,24]. Conversely, gellan gum, a linear and anionic polysaccharide, stands out due to its rapid gelation, ability to increase yield stress and capacity to enhance viscoelastic properties, thus improving filament formation, shape fidelity, and mechanical stability in 3D printed constructs [25–27]. Nonetheless, gelatin and gellan gum do not possess the mechanical properties required to withstand the forces exerted on natural bone or the complex structuration of the ECM of native tissue, highlighting the need for reinforcing agents within the structure. Research indicated compression moduli for these materials usually in the range of 10–200 kPa, far lower than that of native bone, of 100 MPa to 2 GPa. [28,29]. Moreover, it is well known that cells are inherently sensitive to surface chemistry, topography, and rigidity; therefore, in addition to its role in structural and mechanical stability, reinforcement also serves a biological function in ensuring long-term scaffold response and success [30].

A promising reinforcement material for BTE and 3D printing process is cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs), a biodegradable, biocompatible, hydrophilic derivative of cellulose. Owing to their very high length-to-diameter ratio, CNFs represent a sustainable material with a highly reactive surface, capable of increasing the tensile, flexural, and compressive strengths of the structures and allowing the modulation of the rheological properties for high fidelity printed objects [31]. Additionally, another important feature of CNFs is their ability to induce anisotropy in the scaffold, an indispensable feature for mimicking natural bone tissue [32–34]. However, the employment of CNFs is insufficient for overcoming the mechanical limitations of polymer-based bone substituents. Hence, extensive studies have reported the use of different reinforcing agents like calcium phosphates [35,36], silica [37,38], bioactive glass [39], or metal nanoparticles [40]. Among the nanomaterials that have been intensively investigated in the recent years, graphene and graphene derivatives have distinguished themselves owing to their outstanding properties, as they have been demonstrated

to not only result in a remarkable improvement in mechanical properties but also induce osteogenic activity and even promote mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) differentiation for BTE [41–44]. Amine (NH₂) functionalization is a well-known graphene grafting method because of its improved biocompatibility and cell attachment, whereas carboxyl (COOH) group grafting is recognized for its increased water-dispersibility as well as high biocompatibility [45–47]. In their study from 2024, Gholami et al. indicated through molecular dynamics simulations that the incorporation of COOH functional groups enhances the interaction between graphene sheets and the head group of the cell membrane, thereby increasing the ability of graphene to serve as a carrier for targeted delivery to specific cells [48].

The selection of suitable materials is not the only decisive factor in BTE, and the choice of an adequate scaffold fabrication method also plays a key role. Conventional fabrication techniques present limitations in terms of mimicking the complex geometry and porosity of natural bone; therefore, 3D printing has distinguished itself as the most promising method because of its ability to modulate the architecture and porosity of the scaffolds, enabling a personalized approach for tissue regeneration [49,50]. However, for efficient 3D printing of bone substitutes, ink formulations and printing parameters must be carefully tailored to obtain rheological properties suitable for high fidelity 3D printing of stable structures capable of supporting the bone mechanical load, while also maintaining high biocompatibility [51,52].

To meet these requirements, we propose novel complex ink formulations, based on gelatin and gellan gum, double reinforced with CNFs, and two functionalized graphene derivatives, i.e., COOH-GO and NH₂-rGO. The 3D printed scaffolds were subjected to crosslinking and analyses, which demonstrated not only high shape fidelity, proper porosity, modulable degradation, good mechanical properties, and biocompatibility, but also calcium deposition capabilities, which are an indicator of early osteogenic potential. Moreover, the results indicate the superiority of the GC-CBX/AMN samples in terms of the aforementioned properties. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first comparative study to investigate the effects of NH₂-rGO and COOH-GO nanoreinforcing agents on the mechanical, morphological, structural, rheological, and biological properties of scaffolds for bone regeneration.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Gelatin from cold-water fish skin, gellan gum (Gelzan™ CM), calcium chloride dihydrate (CaCl₂ · H₂O, ≥99.0 % purity), genipin (≥98 % powder), and NH₂-rGO were acquired from Sigma Aldrich Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). COOH-GO (~99.0 % purity, ~5.0 % COOH ratio) was supplied by ACS Materials LLC (Pasadena, CA, USA) and 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1-piperidinyloxy (TEMPO) oxidized CNFs (1 wt%) were purchased from Novarials Co. (Woburn, MA). Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM), fetal bovine serum (FBS) and penicillin-streptomycin were acquired from R&D Systems (Minneapolis, MN, USA). The 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) salt assay was supplied by Serva Electrophoresis GmbH (Heidelberg, Germany), whereas the CyQUANT lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) cytotoxicity assay and the Live/Dead Viability/Cytotoxicity kit were supplied by Invitrogen (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Alizarin Red, phosphate buffer solution (PBS), acetic acid, ammonia and Triton-X were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2. Preparation of the ink formulations

Printable ink formulations were obtained starting from a 0.4 % (w/v) TEMPO oxidized CNFs gel with the addition of graphene-based materials in a proportion of 0.5 % (w/v) with respect to the total polymer concentration, as shown in Table 1. To ensure the proper dispersion of

Table 1
Material concentrations of the multicomponent ink formulations.

Code	CNFs (%) w/v)	Gelatin (%) w/v)	Gellan Gum (%w/v)	NH ₂ -rGO ^a (%w/v)	COOH-GO ^a (%w/v)
GC	0.40 %	6.40 %	1.60 %	–	–
GC-AMN	0.40 %	6.40 %	1.60 %	0.50 %	–
GC-CBX	0.40 %	6.40 %	1.60 %	–	0.50 %
GC-CBX/AMN	0.40 %	6.40 %	1.60 %	0.25 %	0.25 %

Abbreviations: CNFs = cellulose nanofibrils; COOH-GO = carboxyl-functionalized graphene oxide; NH₂-rGO = amine-functionalized reduced graphene oxide.
^a with respect to the polymer concentration.

the reinforcing agents, the suspensions were ultrasonicated (VCX 750 ultrasonic from Sonics & Materials, Inc., Newton, CT, USA) for 120 min at 25 % amplitude and a 15s/5s pulse/pause regime in an ice bath. Further, 1.60 % (w/v) gellan gum was added under magnetic stirring at 70 °C, after which 6.40 % (w/v) gelatin was introduced into the mixture at 40 °C. For the control group, all the previous steps were followed, with the exception of the addition of graphene-based compounds. The coding of the multicomponent inks obtained is listed in Table 1. The control group (GC) contained the polymeric matrix and CNFs as the only reinforcement agent, while the other samples presented additional graphene-based reinforcements with codes GC-CBX for the COOH-GO reinforced formulations, GC-AMN for the NH₂-rGO reinforced ones, and GC-CBX/AMN for the samples containing both graphene derivatives.

2.3. Printing parameters optimization and scaffolds fabrication

Once the four multicomponent formulations were obtained, they were loaded into 3 mL plastic cartridges (Cellink, Sweden). The printing process was performed on a BIO X6 3D bioprinter (Cellink, Gothenburg, Sweden) in a temperature-controlled configuration to provide a consistent temperature distribution of 40 °C for both the cartridge and printing nozzle. High-precision needles of inner diameter (ID) 23G (0.33 mm) were attached to the cartridges, and the appropriate pressure and printing speed were determined for each ink. The infill density was set to 25 % and structures of both 10 × 10 × 3 mm and 10 × 10 × 5 mm (length × width × height) were obtained. All scaffolds were first immersed in a 2 % CaCl₂ solution for 30 min for physical cross-linking of gellan gum [53], and then in a 1 % genipin solution for 24 h to allow the formation of covalent bonds between the amino groups of gelatin [54]. Finally, the samples were washed with ultrapure water and after removal of the excess water they were frozen overnight at –20 °C and freeze-dried at –90 °C and 0.05 mbar pressure for 24 h for further evaluation.

2.4. Rheological characterization

The rheology of the inks was examined using a Kinexus Pro rheometer (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK), equipped with a Peltier element for temperature control and parallel plate geometry with a diameter of 20 mm. Viscosity as a function of shear rate was investigated by measurements at a constant shear stress in the shear rate interval of 0.01 and 1000 s⁻¹. The Ostwald-de Waele rheological model in the 0.1–100 s⁻¹ interval was calculated according to Eq. (1), where τ is the shear stress (Pa), K is the consistency index (Pa s ^{n}), γ is the shear rate (s⁻¹) and n is the flow behavior index:

$$\tau = K\gamma^n \quad (1)$$

where τ is the shear stress (Pa), K is the consistency index (Pa s ^{n}), γ is the shear rate (s⁻¹) and n is the flow behavior index.

The recoverability of the hydrogel inks was evaluated by monitoring

the changes in the viscosity values in a three interval thixotropy test. In stage one, a low shear rate (0.1 s⁻¹) was employed for 60s. In the second stage, a high shear rate (100 s⁻¹) was applied for 10s. And, in the third stage, the shear rate was decreased at the initial value of 0.1 s⁻¹ for another 180s. The recovery of viscosity capacity was calculated after 1 min using Eq. (2):

$$\text{Recovery} = \frac{\text{viscosity after 60 seconds}}{\text{initial viscosity}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Dynamic oscillatory measurements were performed in the amplitude and frequency sweeps. In the amplitude sweep, the frequency was set constant at 1 Hz. Using oscillatory tests, the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli were determined in the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) with frequency sweeps varying from 0.1 to 10 Hz. All measurements were performed using a fixed gap (0.5 mm) at 40 °C, and a water-lock system was employed to prevent dehydration of the samples.

2.5. Printability evaluation

The printability assessment of the four inks was carried out according to the method described by Wu et al. [55,56]. ImageJ software was used to measure the mesh area and height of the structures to determine the accuracy of the samples in relation to the theoretical model. To determine the fidelity of the mesh area (F_{ma}), the ratio between the mesh area measured in the experiments (A_e) and the mesh area measured on the theoretical 3D model (A_t) was calculated as described by Eq. (3). Furthermore, the fidelity of height (F_H) was calculated based on the height of the printed structure (H_e) and the height measured using the theoretical 3D model (H_t), as described by Eq. (4).

$$F_{ma}(\%) = \frac{A_e}{A_t} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$F_H(\%) = \frac{H_e}{H_t} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

2.6. Morphological investigations

Morphological evaluation of the scaffolds was performed using a Hitachi TM4000plus II Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan) and TM4000 software (version 1.5). First, freeze-dried scaffolds were coated with a thin conductive gold layer (6 nm) using SEM LUXOR Au/Pt coating equipment (IB-FT GmbH, Berlin, Germany). The surface morphology was studied by employing backscattered electron (BSE) signals in the conductor operation mode at accelerating voltage of 15 kV.

The internal microstructure of the 3D-printed scaffolds was analyzed using micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) with a Bruker SkyScan 1272 high-resolution system. Freeze-dried samples were scanned over 180° rotation at 50 kV and 200 μ A with a rotation step of 0.2°. Each 2D projection was averaged from three acquisitions of 200 ms. The scanning resolution was set to 7 μ m (image pixel size). From the raw data, tomograms were reconstructed using Bruker's NRecon software and visualized using CTvox. Further qualitative analysis and layer separation were conducted through additional processing using CTAn and DataViewer.

2.7. Structural analysis

The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of the samples were obtained using a Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) equipped with an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory. The spectra encompassed the wavenumber range from 4000 to 600 cm⁻¹, with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 32 scans for each sample. FTIR spectra were plotted using OriginPro 9.0.

Furthermore, the phase composition was investigated by X-ray

diffraction (XRD) using a Malvern-PANalytical Empyrean system (Almelo, Netherlands) equipped with a CuK α radiation source of 1.54065 Å wavelength. The samples were analyzed in the range of 5°–60° 2 θ angle, with a step size of 0.026°, a time per step of 0.5s, and spinning at a revolution speed of 0.5s. The inter-layer spacing d was calculated according to Bragg's law, as shown in Eq. (5), where n represents the reflection order, λ is the X-ray wavelength, and θ is the diffraction angle.

$$n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta \quad (5)$$

The mean size of the ordered domains τ was determined by applying Eq. (6), where K represents the shape factor (constant), and FWHM is the full width at half maximum.

$$T = \frac{K\lambda}{\text{FWHM} \cos \theta} \quad (6)$$

2.8. In vitro degradation studies

For the degradation study, freeze-dried 3D printed scaffolds were weighed (W) and then submerged in PBS (pH 7.4) at 37 °C for 7 and 14 days. The samples were collected, rinsed with deionized water, dried for 24h at 40 °C and weighed (W_1). The remaining weight of the samples was measured using Eq. (7).

$$\text{Remaining weight}(\%) = \frac{W_1}{W} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

2.9. In vitro swelling studies

The swelling kinetic studies were conducted by weighing the freeze-dried 3D printed scaffolds (W_0) and immersing them in PBS, at pH 7.4 and 37 °C. At the appropriate time intervals, the swollen scaffolds were weighed after removing the excess liquid (W_i). Eq. (8) was used to calculate the degree of swelling at a given time.

$$\text{Swelling degree}(\%) = \frac{W_i - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

2.10. Mechanical properties evaluation

The mechanical properties of the scaffolds were evaluated on a Discovery 850 DMA TA Instruments analyzer (New Castle, DE, USA) in two different setups, a tensile test setup, equipped with a tensile clamp, designed for uniaxial deformation investigations, and a compression setup, using a compression clamp kit. These tests were carried out on mold-cast samples to investigate the mechanical properties of the materials without the influence of printing parameters such as filament thickness, extrusion pressure, or printing speed. The tensile tests were performed on rectangular specimens ($l = 4$ mm, $w = 2$ mm) at 5 mm/min. These tensile tests were performed on three samples of each scaffold type, and the average values are reported. For practical purposes, only one curve from each set, whose parameters were closest to the mean values, is presented in the graphs. Compression clamps ($\varphi = 40$ mm) were installed on the DMA instrument mentioned above to analyze the compressive strength of the synthesized structures. The disc-shaped scaffolds ($l = 4$ mm, $d = 1$ mm) were first swollen at equilibrium and then subjected to a compression test. The disks were analyzed at a constant compression rate of 2 mm/min until scaffold fracture occurred. Compression measurements were performed on three specimens of each type. To improve readability, the graphs display only one curve from each set using the parameters closest to the mean values. Young's modulus was calculated from the initial tilt of the tensile stress-strain curve.

2.11. In vitro cell viability and differentiation assays

MG63 osteoblast-like cells (CLS, Heidelberg, Germany) were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % penicillin-streptomycin under standard temperature and humidity conditions (37 °C, 5 % CO₂, and 90 % humidity). Cells were seeded at a concentration of 100,000 cells/500 μ L/well in a 24-well plate and incubated under standard temperature and humidity conditions for 24 h to allow cell adhesion. Prior to the assays, the bone regeneration scaffolds were sterilized by UV irradiation for 1h on each side. The samples were then placed in direct contact with MG-63 cells and incubated for 4, 7, and 14 days. The culture medium was supplemented with 2 mL to fully submerge the samples. Cells were incubated under standard temperature and humidity conditions, after which cell viability and differentiation were investigated.

Cell viability was investigated using an MTT assay. After the incubation period, the medium was removed from the well, replaced with MTT solution and incubated for 2h under standard conditions. This solution was prepared by dissolving 10 % MTT (5 mg/mL in PBS) in complete DMEM. After incubation, the MTT culture medium was removed, and the formazan crystals were solubilized with DMSO. The resulting formazan was quantified by spectrophotometric measurement of the absorbance at 570 nm wavelength. Cell viability was calculated relative to the control sample. Furthermore, an LDH release assay was conducted. After the incubation period, 50 μ L of the supernatant from each well was collected and added to a 96-well plate to measure LDH released from the cells upon interaction with the samples. To measure the LDH released following exposure to the 3D printed scaffolds, a CyQUANT LDH Cytotoxicity Assay was employed. Absorbance was measured at 490 nm, and the amount of LDH released was calculated relative to that of the control sample.

For the qualitative assessment, through Live/Dead fluorescence staining assay, the cells were seeded at a concentration of 100,000 cells/well, in 12-well plates, and incubated under standard conditions for 24 h to allow adhesion. The scaffolds, sterilized as previously mentioned, were placed in direct contact with the cells, and the Live/Dead assessment was performed at 4, 7, and 14 days using the Live/Dead assay kit. The staining solution was prepared following the manufacturer's indications and the samples were incubated in the dark for 40 min at room temperature to ensure adequate staining. All microscopy visualization images were acquired using an inverted phase contrast microscope (DMIL LED Fluo model with DFC450-C capture system, Leica, Germany).

Cell differentiation was assessed by measuring the degree of mineralization of the cell cultures following exposure to 3D printed samples. For this purpose, Alizarin Red staining assay of calcium deposits was performed. Following incubation, the samples were removed, and the cells were washed with PBS and fixed with 3.7 % paraformaldehyde in PBS overnight at 4 °C. The cells were then washed with PBS and stained for 45 min with 40 mM Alizarin Red solution. The dye was subsequently removed, and the cells were rinsed with deionized water to remove any unreacted dye. The cells were then incubated with a 10 % acetic acid solution to dissolve the dye that had reacted with the calcium deposits for 1h by shaking horizontally. The supernatant from each sample was collected, sealed with mineral oil, and incubated for 10 min at 85 °C. The resulting solution was then collected, and acetic acid was neutralized with a 10 % ammonia solution.

The negative control comprised cells incubated with complete culture medium only, and the positive control consisted of 1 % Triton-X in the complete culture medium.

2.12. Statistical analysis

All results were obtained in triplicate and are expressed as the average of these values. Moreover, data were expressed as standard deviation (SD) and statistical evaluation was performed using the Student t-test function, for which * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$

were assigned.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Rheological evaluation

An ideal material for extrusion-based 3D printing should exhibit shear-thinning behavior, also known as pseudoplasticity, which is described by a decrease in viscosity with an increase in shear rate [57, 58]. As a consequence of their helical-structure, some polysaccharides such as CNFs, gellan gum, xanthan gum and k-carrageenan present intrinsic properties of orientation in the flow direction when they are under shear rate [59]. Fig. 1(A) presents the variation in viscosity depending on shear rate, and it can be observed that viscosity decreases with the increase in shear for all formulations. Furthermore, rotational rheology data demonstrated that the addition of graphene derivatives influences viscosity, and the results fit the Ostwald-de Waele rheological model in the $0.1\text{--}100\text{s}^{-1}$ interval, with its parameters displayed in Table 2. Ostwald-de Waele describes time-independent non-Newtonian fluids, and all investigated inks exhibited a pseudoplastic behavior with values of $n < 1$. Smaller values of n indicate more pronounced shear-thinning behavior, as displayed by the GC-CBX/AMN formulation. The consistency index value (K), which represents a measure of the integrity of the scaffold with an increase in the number of layers, indicates that graphene reinforcement leads to improved structural integrity even for scaffolds with a high number of layers. Moreover, the correlation coefficient values (R^2) were greater than 0.99, thus demonstrating the consistent adequacy of the data.

A static shear condition was used to perform a thixotropic test to investigate the capacity to maintain viscosity after printing. The

Table 2

Rheological parameters of ink formulations.

Ink code	n	k	R^2	Tan(δ) 10Hz	Recovery after 60 s (%)
GC	0.10	42.68	0.99	0.09	34.43
GC-AMN	0.13	95.34	0.99	0.10	45.82
GC-CBX	0.25	81.10	0.99	0.12	74.69
GC-CBX/AMN	0.07	63.64	0.99	0.11	76.15

recovery of viscosity capacity is shown in Fig. 1(B), and the values are presented in Table 2. The recovery rate after the application of high shear, which mimics the necessary force for extrusion, is enhanced with the addition of graphene derivatives owing to the thixotropic nature of graphene [60,61]. A higher percentage of recovery was observed for the sample reinforced with COOH-GO than with NH_2 -rGO, and a possible explanation for this behavior may be attributed to the ability of COOH-GO to form stronger hydrogen bonds and electrostatic interactions with the polymeric chains [62].

Dynamic oscillatory rheology was used to observe the viscoelastic behavior of the inks. It is considered that a material that presents a G' higher than G'' indicates a solid-like behavior, while a G' lower than G'' is related to liquid-like behavior. To assess ink behavior, the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) was determined in the amplitude sweep. In the LVR domain (Fig. 1(C)), all formulations presented solid-like behavior, which is a characteristic required for extrusion-based 3D printing. This behavior is likely caused by the formation of bond and non-bond interactions between the formulation components, as indicated later in the current paper in Fig. 5(A). At $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the gel-like behavior can be mainly attributed to gellan gum owing to the formation of a double helix. Consequently, the non-covalent interactions that appear between gellan

Fig. 1. Rheological characterization of the ink formulations. (A) Shear rate sweep. (B) Three interval thixotropy test. (C) Amplitude sweep. (D) Frequency sweep.

gum and the other components, especially graphene derivatives, strongly influence the behavior of the inks. Based on the structural investigations, it is the opinion of the authors that -NH_2 functional groups form electrostatic interactions with the -COOH groups available in the gellan gum chain, thus possibly hindering the capacity of double helix formation [63,64]. Next, frequency sweep analysis was carried out in the LVR interval to determine if the formulations had a stable gel-like behavior (Fig. 1(D)). In the investigated range of 0.1–10 Hz, G' and G'' are almost independent of the frequency, which suggests that all inks exhibit stable gel-like behavior. Another important aspect of extrusion 3D printing is related to the loss tangent ($\tan(\delta)$), where higher values are associated with greater shape retention. Table 2 presents the values of $\tan(\delta)$ at 10 Hz, and the highest value was observed for GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN, which suggests that these formulations are expected to exhibit the highest printing fidelity.

3.2. Printability characterization

The four ink formulations were tested at different extrusion pressures and printing speeds to achieve the maximum attainable printability. In 3D extrusion printing, the term printability refers to filament formation, shape fidelity, and the ability to maintain shape post-deposition [65,66]. The optimized parameters for each ink are given in Table 3. Briefly, 3 and 5 mm height samples were produced with the highest printing pressures being required for GC-AMN formulations, where values in the range of 90–110 kPa were necessary to obtain high-fidelity structures. The GC-CBX samples required low pressure values, comparable to the control (GC), whereas, in the case of GC-CBX/AMN formulations, the influence of NH_2 -rGO resulted in the need for pressures in the range of 60–80 kPa to obtain enhanced fidelity structures.

The first evaluation performed was a qualitative assessment, through observation of filament formation (Fig. 2(A*)), to determine the ink's potential to produce a continuous filament. Following extrusion of the GC control ink, liquid-like behavior was observed, initially forming a droplet and not a strand. This behavior is specific to low viscosity solutions, which may prevent the deposition of a continuous filament on the substrate. However, after extended extrusion, the same material displayed the ability to form filaments. The correlation between the filament-forming capabilities and the viscosity of the solution can also be observed for the GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN inks, which exhibited the best results in this respect and possessed a higher viscosity owing to the presence of the graphene reinforcing agents [55,56]. To assess the printing fidelity, two parameters, F_{ma} and F_{H} , were evaluated by processing the images using the Image J software to acquire the measurements and following the equations described in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4). F_{ma} was calculated based on 10×10 mm matrix lattice structures with a 25 % infill density by comparing the area of the printed mesh with the ideal theoretical model. The results graphically represented in Fig. 2(B) indicate an increase in the fidelity of the mesh area for the graphene-reinforced samples; the best results were recorded for the sample double reinforced with both graphene types, GC-CMX/AMN, at 79.0 ± 5.1 %. The lowest performance was observed for the control sample with only 63.2 ± 7.7 %, followed by GC-CBX with 77.2 ± 6.0 % and GC-AMN with 70.8 ± 7.5 %. Similar results were obtained for the height-based printing fidelity evaluation, with the most successful

outcomes for the GC-CBX/AMN sample. F_{H} indicates the degree of fusion and collapse between layers, and in order to obtain structures with high reproducibility and stability, its value must be as close as possible to 100 %. Only $10 \times 10 \times 5$ mm structures were used to evaluate this parameter, and the results are plotted in Fig. 2(C). The GC control sample reached a 104.9 ± 4.5 % height fidelity, corresponding to a printed structure much taller than the ideal theoretical model, which can be attributed to filament over-extrusion due to the low viscosity of the formulation, causing the material to flow more readily than intended, even under low printing pressures [67]. Outcomes closer to optimum values were achieved for the GC-AMN, GC-CBX, and GC-CBX/AMN structures with F_{H} percentages of 97.7 ± 3.4 %, 98.6 ± 4.1 % and 100.6 ± 1.6 % respectively. The high printing fidelity of the GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN formulations is in accordance with the results obtained in the rheology studies regarding the value of $\tan(\delta)$.

3.3. Morphological evaluation

SEM images of the freeze-dried scaffolds were acquired to further characterize the 3D printed shape preservation after freeze-drying, as well as the surface morphology and porosity of the structures. As illustrated in Fig. 3(A), all scaffolds displayed a regular mesh structure with no significant differences between each other. However, it can be observed that the freeze-drying process caused a decrease in filament diameter. The theoretical diameter of the filament, given by the inner diameter of the printing nozzle, was 0.330 mm; thus, the most significant decrease was recorded for the control GC sample (0.137 ± 0.027 mm). The GC-CBX/AMN sample displayed the closest value to theoretical model of the printed filament diameter with 0.177 ± 0.034 mm post-lyophilization. Another indicator of shape retention after freeze-drying is mesh pore dimensions. The ideal pattern features a square shape of these pores with a width of 1.95 mm, whereas in the analyzed scaffolds, the sample that maintains closest to this value is GC-CBX/AMN with 1.85 ± 0.03 mm, followed by GC-CBX, GC-AMN and GC with 1.70 ± 0.04 , 1.68 ± 0.03 and 1.67 ± 0.03 , respectively. The four different scaffold types did not distinguish in surface morphology either, as displayed in Fig. 3(B). Although none of the structures present open surface porosity, a rough and irregular topography can be observed, resembling the complexity of natural bone, which is anticipated to promote cell adhesion. Nevertheless, the cross-sectional images (Fig. 3(C)) revealed the existence of interconnected porosity, without pores of regular shape or size, but with a lamellar microstructure forming channels essential for nutrient transport, cell migration and proliferation.

Micro-CT was utilised to non-destructively analyze the internal morphology of the freeze-dried scaffolds in three dimensions. This method facilitated concurrent qualitative visualization and quantitative assessment of regional disparities in porosity, layer thickness, and dimensional accuracy, which are essential for comprehending scaffold performance and stability. The printability characteristics of the four ink formulations directly influenced the structural variations observed across the bottom, median, and top layers in the CT analysis, with notable differences in dimensional stability, porosity, and containment layer thickness. These variations reveal complex interactions between material deposition, inter-layer bonding and freeze-drying effects, which can manifest differently depending on the viscosity of the ink, reinforcement content, and, perhaps, optimized extrusion parameters.

First, some variations (bottom to top) can be observed in terms of the final angle provided by each deposited filament layer (Fig. 4(A) subsets). Moreover, full side-view tomograms (Fig. 4(B)), demi-top images of the outer layers (Fig. 4(C)), and close-ups of the central square grid (Fig. 4(D)) are displayed for qualitative assessment. A detailed evaluation of individual layer features, including square diagonal, exterior containment layer thickness, solid wall dimensions, and porosity, underscores the role of print parameters and material properties in determining the dimensional stability and internal structure preservation across different

Table 3
Optimum printing parameterization.

Code	Length \times Width \times Height (mm)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Pressure (kPa)	Printing speed (mm s^{-1})
GC	$10 \times 10 \times 3/10$	40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	50–60	11–12
GC-AMN	$\times 10 \times 5$		90–110	11
GC-CBX			50–60	11–12
GC-CBX/AMN			60–80	12

Fig. 2. Printability evaluation. (A) Printed scaffolds of (a) GC, (b) GC-AMN, (c) GC-CBX, (d) GC-CBX/AMN with (#) side view and (*) filament formation insets. (B) Printing fidelity of the mesh area. (C) Fidelity of the height. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

regions of the printed objects. For easier discussion, three distinct regions were highlighted, each consisting of five deposited filaments (bottom/median/top), while the quantitative data in Fig. 4 (E) subsets indicate the averaged results of each individual layer identified and grouped.

The structural characteristics of the freeze-dried 3D-printed samples revealed significant material-dependent variations that can also be interpreted in light of the computer aided design (CAD) model's designed infill porosity and the behavior of the inks during drying. The model, designed with a 25 % infill, implies that the theoretical porosity (void space ratio) should have initially been approximately 75 % because of the large square grid and minimal filament share. However, the actual porosity values, as measured after freeze-drying, exceeded 88 % across all samples, indicating a significant expansion in the void space caused by pore patterning kinetics during the drying process.

Apart from the morphological highlights investigated per region, it can be observed that the tomogram volumes (and particular heights) of interest per layers varied substantially in the three stacked regions. The bottom layers in all samples show a reduced number of slices, indicating that compaction is a consistent issue influenced by the printing process and upper-part material weight. This effect is less pronounced in the reinforced samples, especially GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN, where graphene reinforcement likely enhances the structural support and load distribution. The median and top layers generally retain a higher slice count, while reinforced inks maintain a consistent thickness across layers, suggesting enhanced resistance to both printing-induced and freeze-drying deformation.

Shrinkage differences are very clear in the blend versus nanocomposites, as compaction is more notable at the bottom in samples with lower viscosity (such as GC), while a greater tendency for thinning at the top is displayed. Conversely, GC-CBX/AMN samples retain a more uniform thickness across all layers, raising the issue of the importance of

reinforcement and optimized viscosity in maintaining structural stability throughout the additive manufacturing and freeze-drying processes. As shown in panel (E), the quantitative analysis is complemented by histograms representing the average pore diameters measured both within the preserved square grid and inside the printed filaments across all 15 layers, highlighting trends in pore patterning relative to scaffold height.

The GC control sample displayed considerable structural instability, with low extrusion pressure (50–60 kPa) and low viscosity resulting in uneven layer shrinkage and deformation during freeze-drying. The square diagonal exhibited significant reduction from 1.77 mm at the base to 1.54 mm at the top, indicating poor inter-layer cohesion and inadequate filament formation. The exterior containment layer progressively thinned from 0.71 mm to 0.51 mm, while the pore diameter declined from 234.14 μm to 199.21 μm . Porosity slightly decreased from 93.42 % to 92.83 %, reflecting the overall compaction and increased formation of small pores in the higher layers.

In contrast, the GC-AMN sample exhibited improved structural stability, requiring higher extrusion pressures (90–110 kPa). The square diagonal reduced from 2.97 mm to 1.92 mm, with a moderate decrease in boundary filament thickness from 0.55 mm to 0.47 mm. The pore diameters contracted from 203.29 μm to 185.70 μm , while the porosity stabilized at approximately 88–89 %. This suggests enhanced filament integrity and resistance to pore expansion under drying stress. The solid wall thickness remained consistent (~28.90 μm), reflecting balanced shape fidelity and mechanical stability across layers.

Similarly, the GC-CBX formulation demonstrated high dimensional stability with minimal variation in the square diagonal dimensions (1.67 mm–1.66 mm). The exterior containment layer exhibited only slight fluctuation, ranging from 0.63 mm to 0.71 mm. Pore diameters reduced from 215.15 μm to 190.31 μm , while solid wall thickness (28.21–28.54 μm) and porosity (~93 %) remained relatively constant.

Fig. 3. SEM images of the freeze-dried 3D printed scaffolds. (A) Top view. (B) Surface structure. (C) Cross-sectional. At 1 mm, 100 μm and 300 μm scale (from left to right).

This reflects the beneficial effect of graphene reinforcement, which improves the structural resistance to shrinkage and deformation by enhancing inter-layer adhesion and filament stabilization.

The dual-reinforced GC-CBX/AMN sample exhibits the highest structural fidelity. Unique among the samples, its square diagonal slightly increased from 1.98 mm to 2.10 mm, suggesting superior resistance to shrinkage. The exterior layer remained stable, ranging between 0.65 mm and 0.67 mm. Solid wall thickness (28.18–28.65 μm) remained uniform, while average pore diameters slightly increased from 204.98 μm to 216.75 μm , indicating efficient stress redistribution. The porosity increased from approximately 90.10 % at the bottom to 93.35 % at the top, aligning with a height fidelity score of 100.6 %. This highlights the optimal printability, near-ideal structural reproducibility, and minimal deformation across layers.

The micro-CT data underscore that formulation-dependent variations in porosity, compaction, and layer stability directly influence the scaffold's functional performance. The denser lower regions found in less viscous formulations may hinder nutrient transfer and long-term integration, whereas the more uniform structure of reinforced inks enhances mechanical stability and structural integrity. Micro-CT non-destructively captures internal gradients, offering essential insights into the relationship between printing parameters, material properties, and scaffold functionality. Alongside SEM, this assessment confirmed the observations reported in the printability studies and demonstrated that GC-CBX/AMN scaffolds maintained the highest fidelity to the ideal model, with favorable porosity for cell infiltration, attachment and proliferation.

3.4. Structural characterization

FTIR analysis was performed to explore the chemical interactions

and structural modifications within the 3D printed scaffolds composed of gelatin, gellan gum, reinforced with CNFs and graphene derivatives, and double crosslinked with genipin and CaCl_2 . Fig. 5(A) illustrates the interactions between these components, which are mainly governed by the crosslinking agents and non-bond interactions and the proposed chemical structure of the studied materials based on the FTIR investigation. The spectra displayed in Fig. 5(B) reveal distinct peaks corresponding to various molecular vibrations associated with the backbone and functional groups of the components. Notably, the presence of amide groups was evident in all the spectra. The amide A and B bands of gelatin, observed at $\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 3050\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, were likely overlapped by the broad O–H stretching regions associated with gellan gum and CNFs. The C–H stretching vibrations observed between 2850 and 2960 cm^{-1} were associated with alkyl groups inherent to the molecular structures of gelatin, gellan gum, and CNFs. The secondary structure of gelatin is usually evidenced by the presence of amide I, II, and III bands, which are indicators of the triple helix structure. The FTIR spectra of the GC scaffold showed only the presence of amide I (1630–1650 cm^{-1}), associated with C=O stretching, and amide II (1530–1540 cm^{-1}), attributed to N–H bending and C–N stretching [68, 69].

The contribution of gellan gum was substantiated by distinct bands in the carbohydrate fingerprint region (1050–1150 cm^{-1}), corresponding to C–O stretching and glycosidic linkages. Additionally, the spectral features within the 800–900 cm^{-1} range are characteristic of CNFs and are associated with β -D-glucopyranose ring vibrations typical of the cellulose backbone [68,70,71].

The addition of graphene derivatives (NH_2 -rGO and COOH-GO) significantly enhanced the amide III-specific C–N stretching bands in the 1280–1290 cm^{-1} range associated with the triple helix structure, which could be an indicator of gelatin renaturation [72,73]. Under

Fig. 4. Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) analysis of freeze-dried 3D-printed scaffolds, combining qualitative and quantitative evaluation: (A) side-view shadow projections highlighting angular deviations between layers and overall scaffold geometry, (B) full side-view tomograms with alternating colours per deposited layer, allowing visualization of layer thickness variations and compaction patterns, (C) demi-top view of the outer layers across bottom, median, and top regions, illustrating structural preservation and filament alignment, (D) central square grid close-up showing stacked regions of interest and the measured inner square diagonal, used to assess dimensional fidelity, (E) quantitative analysis of y-axis variation of *porosity increase relative to the designed infill, exterior containment layer variation vs. CAD thickness (%), square diagonal averaged and layer thickness across the three regions of interest. In addition, two histograms per sample illustrate the variation in average pore diameters measured (i) within the preserved square grid and (ii) within the printed filaments across all 15 deposited layers, providing further insight into pore patterning dynamics. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. (A) Schematic representation of the interactions between the functional groups of the polymeric matrix and the reinforcing agents. (B) FTIR spectra of the 3D printed scaffolds. (C) XRD patterns of the samples. Abbreviations: CNFs = cellulose nanofibrils; COOH-GO = carboxyl functionalized graphene oxide; NH₂-rGO = amine functionalized reduced graphene oxide.

normal conditions, this renaturation is slow and often incomplete due to the entropy loss of chain alignment and the presence of cis-proline residues [74]. Typically, gelatin renaturation can be triggered by two main mechanisms. The first is nucleation, which involves the initial spontaneous formation of a small, stable cluster of aligned polymer chains that facilitates helix growth, a process requiring the overcoming of significant energetic barriers and the presence of sufficient local chain concentration [75,76]. The second mechanism relies on specific chemical interactions that actively facilitate the alignment and stabilization of gelatin chains, thereby lowering the entropic cost and promoting helix formation more efficiently [74,77]. As this effect is not observed in the control samples, the classical nucleation process driven purely by chain concentration and random alignment is unlikely to be the main factor, instead, the addition of graphene derivatives likely facilitates renaturation primarily through specific chemical interactions. Although graphene-based materials offer a large two-dimensional surface that can facilitate the alignment of gelatin chains, specific molecular interactions play a key role in this process. While rGO-NH₂ can bind electrostatically to the negatively charged carboxylate groups on gelatin, GO-COOH could form strong hydrogen bonds with the amide N-H groups of gelatin. These interactions act as precise anchoring points, limiting chain mobility and enforcing proper chain orientation. Additionally, π - π stacking between aromatic residues in gelatin and residual sp² domains in graphene derivatives further promotes molecular ordering conducive to helix formation [75,78]. Together, these specific interactions effectively lower the entropic and energetic barriers for coil-to-helix transition, providing thermodynamic stabilization and kinetic facilitation of the triple-helix renaturation.

Moreover, the enhanced peaks at 1410 cm⁻¹, attributed to C-N bending vibrations, and the band at 1440 cm⁻¹, corresponding to C-H bending vibrations, can be attributed to each used graphene derivatives [69]. The incorporation of graphene derivatives also introduces a new peak at 1198 cm⁻¹, corresponding to C-O-C stretching vibrations, indicating the formation of ester bonds between the functional groups of the polymeric chains and graphene derivatives. The introduction of graphene derivatives also resulted in a shift of the amide II peak from 1529 to 1537 cm⁻¹, a phenomenon known to occur when intermolecular H interactions are formed, and also leading to the formation of a peak at 1675 cm⁻¹, that is more pronounced in the formulation with GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN, indicative of ordered hydrogen bonds between

gelatin molecules in the triple helix.

Furthermore, the X-ray diffractograms plotted in Fig. 5(C) and the corresponding data listed in Table 4 provide information regarding the amorphous and ordered domains within the 3D printed scaffolds. All diffractograms presented a semi-crystalline structure with relatively broad but well-defined peaks. The main peaks, observed at approximately $2\theta \approx 20^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 8^\circ$, are typically associated with gelatin and gellan gum with low structural organization, as reported in previous studies, whereas the peaks detected around $2\theta \approx 14^\circ$ and $\approx 26^\circ$ can be assigned to the CNFs [79–83]. Moreover, the peaks at $2\theta \approx 20^\circ$, specific to gelatin, indicate the reconstruction of the 3D structure of gelatin, whereas the elevated intensity of the $2\theta \approx 8^\circ$ peak within the GC-CBX/AMN sample, compared to the other scaffolds, demonstrates a higher triple-helix relative content [84]. After the incorporation of graphene derivatives, no distinct peaks are visible at $2\theta \approx 10$ – 12° specific to GO or at $2\theta \approx 26^\circ$ characteristic for rGO. The absence of these peaks can be attributed to the overall uniform and random dispersion of graphene derivative sheets within the polymeric matrix, possibly down to few-layered structures, which prevents the formation of large detectable crystalline domains. Additionally, the chemical interactions between graphene derivatives and the polymeric chains disrupt the regular stacking of graphene derivatives sheets, increasing the amorphous character of the material [85]. The low τ values registered for GC-CBX/AMN for both main peaks indicate a slight reduction in size of ordered domains. However, when these data are correlated with high maximum intensity and broad FWHM values, as in the case of the $2\theta \approx 8^\circ$ peak in GC-CBX/AMN, the presence of short-range ordered domains

Table 4

XRD measurements of FWHM, d-spacing and τ for peaks at $2\theta \approx 20^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 8^\circ$.

Sample	Band at 2θ	2θ	FWHM	d (nm)	τ (nm)
GC	$\sim 8^\circ$	7.88	2.75	1.121	2.90
GC-AMN		7.93	2.78	1.114	2.87
GC-CBX		7.56	2.75	1.168	2.91
GC-CBX/AMN		8.19	3.00	1.080	2.66
GC	$\sim 20^\circ$	20.63	4.86	0.431	1.66
GC-AMN		20.54	4.99	0.432	1.62
GC-CBX		20.58	5.00	0.432	1.62
GC-CBX/AMN		20.71	5.12	0.429	1.58

can be implied [86,87]. The low FWHM and high τ values recorded for GC-CBX indicate a more ordered structure, which may lead to increased stability and enhanced mechanical properties of these scaffolds [88].

Both structural analyses suggested the renaturation of gelatin following the addition of both graphene derivatives, with the enhancement of the amide III-specific C-N band in the FTIR spectra and the increased intensity of the peak at $2\theta = 8.19^\circ$ in the XRD diffractogram of GC-CBX/AMN. This recovery to a gelatin-like structure within the biomaterial enhanced the functionality of the 3D printed scaffold, improving the overall stability and mimicking the native ECM.

3.5. In vitro degradation and swelling studies

Assessing the degradation and swelling capacity of the scaffolds is needed in order to determine their potential for mimicking the native bone environment, as the degradation rate must allow new tissue formation, while swelling directly influences the material's rigidity, size, mechanical properties, and interaction with cells [89,90]. The swelling kinetics, maximum swelling degree, and remaining weight after degradation of the scaffolds are displayed in Fig. 6(A) and 4(B), and 4(C), respectively. The high swelling ratio indicates the increased capacity of all samples to absorb fluids, mainly owing to the presence of natural polymers, which are abundant in polar groups. These groups form bonds with H₂O molecules in the first stage, and then absorption continues as a result of the osmotic pressure of the interstitial water [91,92]. These results indicate the contribution of graphene derivatives to the stability of the structures. The GC samples exhibited the most significant weight loss after 14 days, with a remaining weight of only 56.13 %. Moreover, the degradation of these samples can be observed after just 1 h, being the only specimen with mass loss on the first day. The kinetics of these control samples indicate a rapid absorption of fluid in the first minute, followed by a short period of equilibrium and then mass loss 1 h after immersion. In contrast, the GC-AMN samples displayed the highest

maximum swelling degree, which reached equilibrium after 15 min. This result can be attributed to the presence of -NH₂ functional groups that form bonds with water molecules, thus increasing absorption. The GC-AMN samples also presented increased stability after 7 days, with a remaining weight of 95.50 %. However, after 14 days, the mass loss was more significant, with an additional 15.27 % loss, indicating accelerated degradation. The most stable scaffolds appeared to be GC-CBX, with a weight loss of 3.86 % after 7 days, and only 13.89 % after 14 days. This result can be attributed to the increased structural order within these samples and the capacity of the -COO⁻ groups of the COOH-GO to form more bonds with other components than the -NH₂ groups within GC-AMN. Regarding the swelling degree, it seems that COOH-GO reinforcement hinders water absorption, with the GC-CBX samples exhibiting the lowest swelling ratio. Although this reinforcement induces more -COO⁻ groups in the polymeric networks, the decreased swelling might be accounted for by the formation of hydrogen bonds between the graphene derivatives sheets and the polymeric macromolecules, which prevent the formation of linkages with the water molecules [93]. The GC-CMX/AMN scaffolds exhibited a moderate maximum swelling, reaching equilibrium after the first 15 min, and presenting no material loss in the first 24 h. Despite the significant weight decrease in the first 7 days, the degradation of these samples seemed to stabilize, showing the smallest weight difference of only 7.60 % between days 7 and 14.

Even if swelling is required for cell infiltration and nutrient diffusion, an increased degree of water absorption accelerates the hydrolysis degradation process as observed in this study. Moreover, this can negatively influence the mechanical properties, thus compromising the integrity of the structures. Therefore, in this case, the samples with a moderate swelling ratio, that is, GC-CBX and GC-CBX/AMN, exhibited a balance between water absorption and proper degradation rate, indicating their suitability for BTE applications.

Fig. 6. (A) In vitro degradation studies. (B) Maximum swelling degree. (C) In vitro swelling kinetics. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

3.6. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of 3D printed scaffolds were investigated to determine the influence of different graphene derivatives on compressive and tensile resistance. The compression stress-strain curves (Fig. 7(A)) and compressive strength at break results (Fig. 7(B)) indicate that the compression load the scaffolds can withstand before fracturing. It is well recognized that reinforcement with graphene derivatives significantly improves the mechanical properties of the polymeric matrices, allowing a more homogeneous distribution of the compressive forces exerted on the material [94]. In our analysis, this effect is best observed for the GC-CBX sample, which recorded a compressive strength of 299.64 ± 5.03 kPa ($p < 0.001$ compared to control). In contrast, the GC-AMN sample exhibited a lower value of only 243.67 ± 6.02 kPa, which may be attributed to a weaker interaction between NH_2 -rGO and the polymer chains in comparison to the COOH -GO polymer chains. Accordingly, for the GC-CBX/AMN samples, the results indicated a moderate compressive strength of 252.12 ± 17.36 kPa ($p < 0.05$). However, reinforcement with a single graphene derivative does not seem to yield favorable results in tensile testing. The tensile stress-strain curves (Fig. 7(C)) and the tensile strength at break values (Fig. 7(D)) indicate inferior performance for the GC-AMN and GC-CBX samples compared to the control group. Nevertheless, the GC-CBX/AMN samples indicate better tensile strength results, with 184.54 ± 41.75 kPa,

compared to the control sample values of only 140.41 ± 56.59 kPa. These results indicated a synergistic effect of the two types of graphene reinforcement on the tensile resistance. Moreover, the Young's modulus values (Fig. 7(E)) also displayed an increase for the GC-CBX/AMN samples with a value of 10.13 ± 2.63 kPa compared to 7.91 ± 2.03 kPa of the GC group. When the aim is implantation of the scaffold, both compression and tensile strength are vital to achieve the structure's resistance to the mechanical loads to which it will be exposed. Considering this, our mechanical investigations suggest that the GC-CBX/AMN constructs have the highest potential for use in bone regeneration therapies.

3.7. In vitro cell viability and differentiation studies

The biocompatibility of bone regenerative scaffolds is an essential attribute that impacts the cellular response. The MTT cell viability assay characterizes the metabolic behavior of the MG63 cells following exposure to the 3D printed GC and composite scaffolds. The cell viability for each sample was calculated relative to that of the control scaffold. As displayed in Fig. 8(A), within 4 days post exposure of the osteoblast-like cells to the samples, the results indicated a cell viability above 80 %, which indicates a biocompatible behavior according to ISO10993-5:2009 Biological evaluation of medical devices- Part 5: Tests for *in vitro* cytotoxicity. After 7 days of incubation, an increase in

Fig. 7. Mechanical properties of the 3D printed scaffolds. (A) Compression stress-strain analysis. (B) Compression strength at break. (C) Tensile stress-strain analysis with inset of the linear region for Young's modulus calculation. (D) Tensile strength at break. (E) Young's modulus. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. 8. In vitro cell viability and differentiation testing. (A) MTT assay. (B) LDH measurements. (C) Alizarin Red mineralization assessment. (D) Optical microscopy images of the osteoblast cultures exposed to the samples for 4 days. (E) Live/Dead fluorescent staining. All assays were performed with MG63 cells after 4, 7, and 14 days of direct contact with the samples. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

metabolic activity was measured compared to control samples, with $11.67 \pm 5.67\%$ for GC-CBX/AMN scaffolds, up to $18.19 \pm 4.5\%$ for GC-CBX and $43.84 \pm 5.72\%$ for the GC-AMN samples ($p < 0.001$ compared to control). Osteoid synthesis is often associated with an increase in the metabolic activity of osteoblasts [95–99]. Thus, following contact with the modified scaffolds, accelerated osteoblast cells' metabolism enables the necessary energy for the differentiation process [99].

After 14 days of incubation in the presence of scaffold samples, the metabolic activity of the osteoblast-like cells was comparable to that of the control samples, with the exception of the GC-AMN scaffold, where cell metabolism increased by approximately 40% compared to the control ($p < 0.001$). Progression of the mineralization process is often associated with a decrease in cell metabolism [100–102]. To further

confirm the results obtained from the MTT assay, an LDH test was performed (Fig. 8(B)). Generally, LDH assay results characterize the effect of cell death associated with destruction of the cell membrane. The measurements in osteoblast cultures exposed to modified scaffolds showed levels of extracellular LDH comparable to control samples, which confirms the biocompatibility of the obtained scaffolds.

The ability of the GC, GC-AMN, GC-CBX, and GC-CBX/AMN scaffolds to promote calcium deposition and support mineralization is fundamental for bone regeneration, as these processes represent early indicators of osteogenesis and contribute to enhanced mechanical stability, facilitating integration within the native bone and supporting functional bone formation. Fig. 8(C) illustrates the mineralization measured with the Alizarin Red assay, which confirmed a statistically

significant increase in the deposition of Ca ions in the extracellular matrix of osteoblast-like cells exposed to GC-CBX/AMN samples at all-time intervals ($p < 0.05$, compared to the control scaffold). For all other modified scaffold samples, the mineralization induction potential of the osteoblast cultures was comparable to that of the control. Further, microscopic investigation of the osteoblast cells (Fig. 8(D)) revealed a normal elongated morphology of the cells following direct exposure to the scaffolds; the cell density was comparable to that of the control samples.

Additionally, Fig. 8(E) displays representative live/dead staining microscopic images acquired after 4, 7, and 14 days of direct contact with the 3D printed scaffolds. Live cells (stained green) were observed to adhere and to exhibit appropriate morphology for all samples starting at day 4, confirming that the scaffolds did not interfere with the normal attachment mechanism of MG63 cells. The images obtained at 7 and 14 days show a progressive increase in cell density for all samples, while only a limited number of non-viable cells (red staining) were detected. These findings are consistent with the results of the MTT and LDH assays and indicate that all 3D printed scaffolds exhibited low cytotoxicity and support proper cell attachment and proliferation.

4. Conclusions

This paper reported the successful synthesis of ink formulations suitable for the fabrication of scaffolds for bone tissue regeneration through 3D printing, allowing us to obtain structures with customizable geometry and high porosity. In terms of printing fidelity, the inks reinforced with both NH_2 -rGO and COOH-GO presented the best performance regarding both the printing fidelity on the mesh area and fidelity on the height, with values of $79.0 \pm 5.1\%$ and $100.6 \pm 1.6\%$ respectively. From a morphological point of view, the GC-CBX/AMN samples also exhibited superior results, with the highest structural fidelity, uniform thickness across all layers, and minimal deformation. Concerning *in vitro* degradation and swelling, the GC-CBX scaffolds displayed better outcomes, with a remaining mass of $86.10 \pm 3.77\%$ after 14 days and a low degree of swelling, whereas GC-CBX/AMN presented more moderate results. These findings are in agreement with the compressive strength evaluations, where a similar trend was observed, with the highest compressive strength for GC-CBX with 299.64 ± 5.03 kPa, closely followed by GC-CBX/AMN with 252.12 ± 17.36 kPa. These results can be attributed to the more ordered structure of GC-CBX, as evidenced by the XRD analysis. However, this tendency was not observed in tensile testing, where GC-CBX/AMN structures exhibited the highest tensile strength of 184.54 ± 41.75 kPa. Moreover, the GC-CBX samples did not show the best results in biocompatibility tests either, with the best performance reported for GC-AMN samples, followed by GC-CBX/AMN. Nevertheless, another important biological aspect is the ability of the scaffold to stimulate mineralization, in which the highest calcium deposition was measured for the GC-CBX/AMN samples at 4–14 days. In conclusion, our findings indicate that the incorporation of both types of graphene derivatives offers the most promising results, as COOH-GO can significantly enhance the mechanical strength, whereas NH_2 -rGO contributes to improved biocompatibility. The GC-CBX/AMN scaffolds exhibited notable improvements across multiple parameters, including increased compressive strength, superior tensile strength, enhanced biocompatibility, and the highest capacity for calcium deposition, highlighting their potential for bone tissue regeneration.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mihaela-Raluca Dobrisan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alin-Georgian Toader:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Elena Alina Chiticaru:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **George**

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtadv.2025.100621>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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